
Capital Expenditure Cost and Economic Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post-factor research design targeted at determining the relationship between capital expenditure cost on education sector and economic development in Nigeria. The population of this study was the entire Nigerian economy where the properties of data used for this research were extracted covering 2003 to 2022. A sample is a part or unit of the population. Using judgmental sampling technique, a sample of 20years' period from 2003 to 2022 was used. Time series secondary data obtained basically from the CBN bulletin and world demographic index for a period of 20years (2003 to 2022) were used. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis on the strength of relationship between the predictors and criterion variable (HDI). Co-integration test was used to determine the long-run effect of the predictors on the criterion variable (HDI). The results revealed a significant positive relationship between health sector expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The results also revealed an insignificant negative relationship between education sector expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The study's long-run test between the variables shows no presence of long-run relationship between the variables. The concluded that a significant relationship exist between health sector expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The also concluded that an insignificant relationship exist between education sector expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The researcher further suggests that the Nigerian government should allocate a larger portion of its budget to healthcare. This funding should be used to upgrade existing healthcare infrastructure, build new healthcare facilities, and equip them with modern medical technologies. The government should increase funding for education and focus on technical and vocational training.

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1 Introduction

Nigeria, as the most populous country in Africa, possesses considerable economic prospects. Nevertheless, the entity in question has encountered a multitude of obstacles over the course of its existence, encompassing instances of political volatility, pervasive corruption, deficiencies in infrastructure, and disparities in economic distribution. Nigeria has seen phases of economic expansion, notably during the period of increased oil production and revenue in the 1970s. The exportation of oil has played a significant role in fostering economic expansion and generating substantial government income. Nevertheless, the nation's over reliance on petroleum has rendered its economy susceptible to swings in oil prices. Nigeria has undertaken initiatives to enhance its educational framework; yet, the issue of attaining quality education persists, particularly in rural regions (Awogbemi, 2023). Gaps in educational access and outcomes exist between urban and rural areas, and gender-based gaps continue to be evident in terms of enrolment rates and literacy levels (Ugochukwu et al., 2021). Nigeria has demonstrated advancements in enhancing healthcare infrastructure; yet, the challenge of ensuring access to high-quality healthcare persists, particularly in geographically isolated and neglected regions. According to Mohammed et al. (2021), health indicators, including life expectancy and maternal mortality rates, have demonstrated improvements; however, they continue to fall short of global standards. The issue of income disparity in Nigeria is a matter of considerable importance. Although certain regions exhibit affluence and a burgeoning middle socioeconomic group, a significant proportion of the populace continues to endure impoverished conditions. Elevated levels of economic disparity have the potential to exert a detrimental influence on the overall Human Development Index (HDI). According to the findings of Useni et al. (2022), Nigeria's economic development has been impeded by factors such as political instability, corruption, and governance challenges. Various factors have the potential to influence the equitable allocation of resources and the efficacy of social and economic programmes. Nigeria has acknowledged the necessity of tackling these concerns. Numerous governmental entities have implemented economic reforms and social initiatives with the objective of enhancing education, healthcare, and infrastructure. Various initiatives have been undertaken to foster economic diversification and reduce reliance on oil. The Human Development Index (HDI) of Nigeria has seen progress throughout time; yet, it continues to fall below the global average. The HDI score of the nation is indicative of advancements achieved in the domains of health and education, however it is impeded by the presence of income disparity and several socio-economic obstacles. The resolution of these difficulties will be of utmost importance for Nigeria's sustained economic growth and advancement in human development. The maintenance of good health is a crucial component of an individual's overall well-being. Given that individuals together form a nation, it follows that healthcare should be considered a fundamental prerequisite for attaining sustainable long-term economic progress. The term "health" can be described

as the whole physical condition of an individual, encompassing both the body and mind, particularly with regard to the presence or absence of illnesses, injuries, or impairments. The topic of health is of significant importance due to its implications for the human population, as it pertains to the well-being and functioning of the human body. The maintenance of good health is crucial for the successful execution of economic activities. In the absence of sound health, the efficiency of such activities is significantly compromised. Therefore, it is imperative to approach this matter with utmost seriousness (Gwaison & Maimako, 2020). The efficacy and cost-effectiveness of healthcare expenditure are of paramount importance. The potential limitations on the human development index (HDI) may arise from inefficient utilisation of funds or a significant prevalence of corruption within the healthcare sector. The human development index (HDI) is a comprehensive composite indicator that incorporates multiple dimensions, including education and income. Investments in the aforementioned domains, with efforts to tackle challenges such as poverty and inequality, are vital for the holistic advancement of human development. The potential effects of augmented expenditure in the health sector may require a significant period of time to manifest. Significant enhancements in health outcomes and, consequently, the human development index (HDI) typically necessitate long-term and consistent investment. Factors such as epidemics, natural disasters, and global economic situations can exert an impact on a nation's human development index (HDI), which cannot be exclusively attributed to domestic healthcare sector investments. Improvements in health care have been shown in the literature to be a necessary precondition for improving human capital development (HCD) in any economy (Awogbemi, 2023). According to the aforementioned perspective, an enhanced state of health within a nation leads to a positive shift in the labour supply curve, resulting in increased productivity in the workforce. Consequently, this rise in productivity extends to investments in various types of human capital. According to Gwaison and Maimako (2020), the extent of government spending on healthcare plays a crucial role in shaping the general advancement of human capital. This, in turn, has a direct impact on the quality and effectiveness of investments made in various sectors of the economy, resulting in improved productivity and efficiency. The government is a societal institution that serves the purpose of ensuring social cohesion and maintaining order within a nation (Adegboye & Oziegbe, 2018). In contrast, education, whether in a formal or informal setting, functions as a significant tool employed by the government to instill in individuals the essential standards, morals, and behavioural patterns required for the collective preservation of the nation. Hence, the degree of a nation's progress holds considerable importance in delineating the role of the Government within a given community. In communities characterised by traditional norms, where education is primarily informal and regarded as a communal obligation, a decentralised or loosely organised system of governance is established to facilitate the comprehensive assimilation of children into the cultural fabric of the community. In a society of this nature, the involvement of the Government in curriculum preparation and implementation may not extend to financial contributions. However, its presence is evident through the enforcement of punishments against those engaging in anti-social activity. In the context of present-day society, Joan et al. (2020) argue that the government's involvement in education has become more extensive. This is evident in its en-

agement in curriculum design and innovations, provision of equipment, personnel, and funding for the purpose of overseeing and regulating individuals and resources. In the present-day society, it is widely recognised that the private sector holds a certain degree of responsibility in societal affairs. However, it is evident that the principal responsibility of the Government is to provide education to its population. Joan et al. (2020) conducted a comprehensive analysis of government expenditure on education and found empirical evidence supporting the positive relationship between educational attainment and employment outcomes. Specifically, their study revealed that individuals with higher levels of education had a greater likelihood of securing work and a reduced risk of job loss, provided they are currently employed. There is a positive correlation between the level of education achieved by individuals and their involvement rate. Individuals that possess the highest level of education attain the highest level of income. Studies examining the impacts of education frequently aim to ascribe variations in individuals' earnings to disparities in their possession of human capital. According to the classic theories of human capital, it is expressly postulated that workers receive compensation based on their marginal output. It is logically inferred that individuals with greater levels of education earn higher salaries due to their presumed higher production (Joan et al., 2020). Countries that prioritise and invest more resources in the education of their inhabitants tend to experience higher levels of economic prosperity compared to those that do not prioritise education. Economies characterised by a significant concentration of highly skilled workers are more likely to swiftly embrace and integrate the most optimal technologies. The educational attainment level plays a crucial role in enhancing the rate of economic growth by expediting the process of technology assimilation. The acquisition of a reservoir of knowledge enables the enhancement of productivity in generating economic prosperity through the utilisation of labour and capital resources. Increasing access to education and, thus, expanding the pool of highly qualified employees capable of contributing to the accumulation of knowledge will enhance the rate of discoveries and subsequently amplify the potential for economic growth. The relationship between capital expenditure on the education sector and the human development index (HDI) in Nigeria can be complex and multifaceted. While increased investment in education is generally associated with improved human development outcomes, such as higher literacy rates, better health, and increased income levels, several factors can influence the impact of capital expenditure on education. It's not just the amount of money spent on education that matters but how effectively it is utilized. If capital expenditure is mismanaged or not directed towards improving the quality of education, it may not have a significant impact on HDI. Capital expenditure can help build schools and infrastructure, but if there are still barriers to access, such as distance or cultural factors, it may not translate into improved education outcomes. Investment in teacher training and hiring qualified educators is crucial for improving the quality of education. If funds are not allocated for this purpose, the impact on HDI may be limited. Updating and improving the curriculum to meet the needs of a changing society and economy is essential. Capital expenditure can support this through the development of educational materials and resources. While education is a significant contributor to HDI, other factors like healthcare and income levels also play a crucial role. Capital expenditure in these sectors can complement education spend-

ing and lead to more significant improvements in HDI. It's important to note that the impact of increased capital expenditure on education may not be immediate. Improving education outcomes often takes time, and the effects may become more evident in the long run. Nigeria faces various socioeconomic challenges, including poverty, inequality, and political instability. These factors can also influence the relationship between education spending and HDI.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria, like many other countries, faces significant challenges in the areas of health and education, which are crucial pillars for economic development. Nigeria's health-care infrastructure faces numerous challenges, such as lack of health care facilities, supplies, and trained healthcare workers, among other issues, especially in rural areas (Adegboye & Oziegbe, 2018). The healthcare system is fragmented, leading to disparities in healthcare access and quality. Nigeria grapples with a high burden of diseases such as malaria, HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and non-communicable diseases. These diseases not only strain the healthcare system but also hinder economic productivity. High maternal and child mortality rates remain a concern. Efforts to improve maternal and child healthcare have been made, but more investment is needed to reduce these rates (Eke et al., 2023). Improving access to vaccines and preventive healthcare measures is crucial to reducing the prevalence of preventable diseases. Access to healthcare is limited for many Nigerians due to the absence of a comprehensive health insurance system (Gwaison & Maimako, 2020). The government has initiated efforts to expand health insurance coverage, but progress has been slow.

Nigeria faces challenges in ensuring universal access to quality education, particularly in rural areas (Joan et al., 2020). There is a significant gender gap in education, with fewer girls attending school compared to boys. The quality of education in Nigeria varies widely, with issues such as overcrowded classrooms, poorly trained teachers, outdated curriculum, and inadequate teaching materials. This affects the effectiveness of education. Awogbemi (2023), stated that adult literacy rates are relatively low in Nigeria, which hinders economic development by limiting opportunities for skill acquisition and job prospects. Nigeria has a number of universities, but they often face issues like strikes, underfunding, and inadequate infrastructure, impacting the quality of higher education. The mismatch between the skills acquired through education and the demands of the labor market is a significant challenge. Many graduates struggle to find jobs that match their qualifications. Hence, these issues and the dearth of literature in this area ignited the zeal to investigate the correlation between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The study specifically sought to;

1. Investigate the relationship between health sector expenditure cost and human development index in Nigeria.
2. Examine the relationship between education sector expenditure cost and human development index in Nigeria.

2 Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Pure Theory of Public Expenditure (Samuelson, 1954)

2.1. Pure Theory of Public Expenditure (Samuelson, 1954) The foundational framework of the theory of government spending was initially presented in a coherent manner in 1955 by Samuelson, an acclaimed economist from the United States. According to Samuelson (1954), the pure theory of public spending maintains the classification of government services while placing emphasis on the particular modes of consumption associated with these services. This idea places emphasis on the necessity of government intervention in instances where markets are unable to effectively distribute resources. The importance of public expenditure in Nigeria's education system is clear, as it plays a critical role in enhancing accessibility and affordability of education for a significant section of the population. The allocation of resources towards education has the potential to generate favourable outcomes for economic progress. Through the allocation of resources to education, the government has the potential to enhance human capital, hence fostering increased productivity, creativity, and economic growth. Nevertheless, the efficacy of educational expenditure in Nigeria may be influenced by factors such as corruption and mismanagement, necessitating their resolution to achieve optimal outcomes. According to the Pure Theory of Public Expenditure, public health is classified as a public good. The presence of government intervention is of utmost importance in guaranteeing the accessibility of healthcare services to the entire Nigerian population. Enhanced allocation of resources in this domain has the potential to enhance health outcomes and mitigate disparities in healthcare access. The presence of a robust population is vital for the advancement of economic growth. The productivity of individuals tends to increase when they are in good health, and the allocation of resources towards healthcare can alleviate the economic impact caused by illness and disease. Nevertheless, Nigeria is confronted with various obstacles pertaining to healthcare infrastructure, accessibility, and quality, necessitating focused investment. The government plays a crucial role in facilitating economic development through capital investment, which encompasses the construction and upkeep of essential infrastructure, including roads, bridges, and energy facilities. The Pure Theory of Public Expenditure provides justification for making investments aimed at mitigating market failures and fostering economic progress. Strategic allocation of capital investment has the potential to generate favourable externalities, hence fostering advantageous outcomes across multiple sectors within the economy. One illustrative instance is the potential of enhanced transport infrastructure to mitigate corporate expenses and foster investment from the private sector. Nigeria has encountered challenges pertaining to corruption and the misallocation of public funds, which have the potential to affect the efficacy of expenditures in the do-

mains of education, health, and infrastructure. It is imperative to address these challenges. Merely allocating monies is inadequate. The equitable provision of education, healthcare, and infrastructural services holds similar significance in promoting efficiency. The implementation of quality improvement methods is crucial. The government of Nigeria frequently encounters fiscal limitations as a result of the volatility in oil prices.

Health sector expenditure and human development index in Nigeria

Capital expenditure in the health sector refers to the government's investment in healthcare infrastructure, equipment, facilities, and other resources aimed at improving the healthcare system. The Health Development Index (HDI) measures a country's overall development based on three key dimensions: life expectancy at birth, mean years of schooling, and per capita income. Increasing capital expenditure in the health sector can lead to improvements in health metrics, such as longer life expectancies and lower rates of death among infants, which contribute positively to the health dimension of the HDI. Research by Awogbemi (2023) supports a clear relationship between the advancement of human capital and the expansion of the economy in Nigeria. The report proposes encouraging private sector investment in healthcare and education to increase their involvement in delivering educational and healthcare services to the broader populace. It is also crucial to enhance welfare programs specifically designed for healthcare workers in Nigeria to decrease suffering experienced by the population and alleviate the possible departure of doctors and other healthcare workers from the country. Owu et al. (2022) used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model to investigate the relationship between government expenditure on education and the advancement of human capital in Nigeria. They found that both recurrent and capital expenditures on health exhibited a positive impact, albeit statistically insignificant. Eke et al. (2023) revealed a significant positive relationship between health sector expenditure and economic development in Nigeria.

Akintunde et al. (2022) found that government spending on health has a negative effect on health outcomes, specifically life expectancy, in the short term but a positive impact in the long term. Babatunde (2018) found a notable impact on Nigeria's economic growth due to government expenditure on health infrastructure. Gwaison and Maimako (2020) conducted a survey to examine the impact of government health expenditures on the performance of the health sector in Nigeria. The study suggests prioritizing capital expenditures in the healthcare sector to promote its rapid development and establishing mechanisms to address corruption, including the diversion and embezzlement of public health funds. This led to hypothesis one which is stated below;

Ha1: There is a significant relationship between health sector expenditure and human development index in Nigeria.

Education sector expenditure cost and human development index in Nigeria

Capital expenditure on the education sector can significantly improve the human development index (HDI) in Nigeria, particularly by improving education indica-

tors. However, this impact depends on various factors, including the effectiveness of investments and their distribution across regions. A comprehensive approach addressing multiple aspects of development is necessary to improve the overall HDI in Nigeria. Recent studies have shown a significant correlation between economic growth and expenditures allocated towards health and education, suggesting that the Nigerian government should prioritize these sectors. This involves allocating a considerable proportion of public expenditure to healthcare and education while fostering employment opportunities through skill enhancement and vocational training. Public infrastructure investment has also been found to positively impact economic growth in Nigeria, with positive associations between public investments in educational infrastructure, power, and technology and the economy. Adeyemi and Ogunsola (2016) found a prolonged positive correlation between secondary school enrollment, lifespan rate, gross capital creation, public education spending, and economic expansion. However, this association did not reach statistical significance. Kenneth et al. (2020) conducted an analysis on the impact of government expenditure on education and school achievement on per capita income from 1990 to 2018. The findings showed statistically significant positive associations between GDP per capita, adult literacy rate, tertiary and secondary school enrollment ratios, government capital investment on education, and the creation of gross fixed assets. Investing in the education sector through capital expenditure is crucial for enhancing human development outcomes in Nigeria. However, it is essential to implement additional complementary initiatives and strategies alongside such investments to ensure substantial improvements in the HDI. This led to hypothesis two which is stated below;

Ha2: There is a significant relationship between education sector expenditure and human development index in Nigeria.

2.2 Literature Gap

The common theories adopted in most of the few existing works on capital expenditure are anchored on the Peacock-Wiseman Theory, Robert Lucas Endogenous Growth Theory. However, this work is basically anchored on pure theory of public expenditure. This theory emphasizes that governments should intervene when markets fail to allocate resources efficiently. Previous studies on this topic adopted time series data, descriptive, collinearity test and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Nevertheless, the present study adopted ex-post-facto research design. Also, co-integration test and multiple regression were used to investigate the available annual time series data to ascertain whether or not there is an existence of causal and long-run relationship between capital expenditure and economic development. Most of the work performed on capital expenditure cost considered its impact on economic growth using the gross domestic product and the per capita income. However, this work is a little deviation from the norm as we considered its relationship, using human development index.

3 Methodology

The study adopted ex-post-factor research design targeted at determining the relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. According to Appah (2020), it was suggested that the target population refers to the complete population to which the study’s findings can be applied. The author further observed that the target population refers to the complete set of items that the researcher intends to investigate and make generalisations about. The population of this study was the entire Nigerian economy where the properties of data used for this research were extracted covering 2003 to 2022. A sample is a part or unit of the population (Odukwu et al., 2022). Using judgmental sampling technique, a sample of 20years’ period from 2003 to 2022 was used. Time series secondary data obtained basically from the CBN bulletin and world demographic index for a period of 20years (2003 to 2022) were used. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis on the strength of relationship between the predictors and criterion variable (HDI). Co-integration test was used to determine the long-run effect of the predictors on the criterion variable (HDI).

3.1 Model Specification

The mathematical representations of the functional relationship that represents our stated hypotheses are expressed as follows:

$$HDI = f(CXHS, CXES) \tag{1}$$

Their econometric expression becomes

$$HDI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CXHS_{et} + \beta_2 CXES_{et} + e_t \tag{2}$$

Where;

HDI = Human development index (Proxy for economic development)

CXHS = Capital Expenditure on health sector

CXES = Capital Expenditure education sector

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = Coefficients attached to explanatory variables

t = Time Period

e = Stochastic Error Term

4 Data analysis and Discussion

4.1 Data Analysis

Data analyzed here were the properties of capital expenditure cost (expenditure on health and education sector) and economic development (RGDP and HCD) in Nigeria.

The study investigated the long-run relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria over a 20-year period. The able above shows no presence of long-run relationship between the variables. This suggests

Table 1: Johansen's co-integration test

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.516894	27.60218	29.79707	0.0877
At most 1	0.399205	14.50684	15.49471	0.0700
At most 2 *	0.256535	5.335806	3.841466	0.0209

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max- Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.516894	13.09534	21.13162	0.4435
At most 1	0.399205	9.171035	14.26460	0.2722
At most 2 *	0.256535	5.335806	3.841466	0.0209

Max-eigenvalue test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

that within the study period, capital expenditure has had no long-run impact on economic development in Nigeria. This could be as a result of corruption practices among machineries of successive government and the inability to utilize the nation's resources in a judicious manner.

Table 2: Dependent variable: HDI

Method: Least Squares				
Date: 09/12/23 Time: 13:30				
Sample: 1 20				
Included observations: 20				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.097563	0.033316	2.928440	0.0094
HLT	0.158653	0.013090	12.11997	0.0000
EDU	-1.16E-05	0.001430	-0.008145	0.9936
R-squared	0.896799	Mean dependent var		0.501700
Adjusted R-squared	0.884658	S.D. dependent var		0.027444
S.E. of regression	0.009321	Akaike info criterion		-6.375717
Sum squared resid	0.001477	Schwarz criterion		-6.226357
Log likelihood	66.75717	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-6.346560
F-statistic	73.86372	Durbin-Watson stat		0.250824
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

In the table above, the R-squared value for our regression model is 0.896799 with the p-value of 0.000 $\leq$ 0.005 level of significance. This suggests that there is a significant positive relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. This indicates that approximately 90% of the variance in the dependent variable (human development index) can be explained by the indepen-

dent variables included in our model (health and education sectors expenditure). In other words, our model accounts for a substantial portion of the variability in economic development, suggesting that it is a reasonably good fit for the data. The table above, also showed the Adjusted R-squared value of 0.88 which indicates that our regression model explains approximately 88% of the variance in the dependent variable. This suggests that our chosen independent variables collectively have a strong influence on the outcome we are studying. The Adjusted R-squared accounts for the complexity of our model by penalizing the inclusion of unnecessary variables, which helps us avoid over-fitting. Therefore, we can be reasonably confident that our model strikes a good balance between explanatory power and simplicity. However, it's important to note that there is still 12% of the variance unexplained by our model, which could be due to unaccounted factors or measurement error.

Test of hypotheses 1&2

The study found a significant relationship between capital expenditure cost on education and economic development in Nigeria, with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.005$, and an insignificant relationship between capital expenditure cost on health sector and economic development, with a p-v of $0.9936 > 0.005$.

4.2 Discussion

The study revealed a significant positive relationship between capital expenditure cost and economic development in Nigeria. The result indicated the predictor variables has 90% of the variance in the dependent variable (human development index) while holding other variables constant. This suggests that the capital expenditure on health and education sector has contributed immensely to the nation's economic development within the study period. The result also advocated that investments in education and healthcare has helped to improve the skills and productivity of the workforce. This result also suggests that capital expenditure on education has not massive as it should be. This result further suggests more investment in the construction of new schools and the provision of better educational facilities. This will increase access to quality education, reducing illiteracy rates and improving the overall human capital of the country. However, it's important to note that the impact of capital expenditure in these sectors may take time to materialize, and it depends on various factors, including the efficiency of spending, the quality of services provided, and the broader economic and political environment. Moreover, while these investments can contribute to economic development, they should be part of a comprehensive development strategy that addresses other economic challenges such as infrastructure, governance, and macroeconomic stability. Investing in healthcare and education in Nigeria is crucial given the country's large population and the potential benefits it can bring in terms of a more skilled and healthy workforce. However, the effectiveness of these investments will also depend on how well they are implemented and integrated into the overall development agenda. This finding is consistent with the studies conducted by Awogbemi (2023) and Okwu et al. (2022), which demonstrated that investment in healthcare infrastructure had a positive but statistically negligible impact. According to Gwaison and Maimako (2020), there is a positive relationship between government overall health expen-

ditures, capital health expenditure, and recurring health expenditures, and the performance of the health sector, as measured by the life expectancy rate. However, this relationship was found to be statistically insignificant. Nevertheless, the relationship between capital health expenditure and life expectancy was shown to be statistically significant. The studies conducted by Bachama et al. (2021), Enya and Ezeali (2021), and Adeyemi and Ogunsola (2016) revealed a sustained positive correlation between secondary school enrollment, public education expenditure, life expectancy, gross capital formation, and economic growth. According to the research conducted by Babatunde (2018), the results suggest that the allocation of government funds towards the development of health infrastructure in Nigeria has a notable impact on the country's economic growth. In a study conducted by Kenneth et al. (2020), it was demonstrated that there exists a positive and statistically significant relationship between capital expenditure on education, secondary school enrollment ratio, tertiary school enrolment ratio, adult literacy rate, and GDP per capita.

5 Conclusion

The study found a significant positive relationship between capital expenditure cost on education and economic development in Nigeria, while an insignificant negative relationship was found between capital expenditure cost on health. This suggests that education has significantly contributed to Nigeria's economic development, while health has not made significant progress. However, the long-run test showed no long-term impact of capital expenditure on economic development, possibly due to corrupt practices and inefficient resource utilization. The study suggests that investing in healthcare and education is crucial for Nigeria's economic growth, as a healthy and educated population is more productive and can contribute significantly to economic growth. The researcher further suggests that;

1. The Nigerian government should allocate a larger portion of its budget to healthcare. This funding should be used to upgrade existing healthcare infrastructure, build new healthcare facilities, and equip them with modern medical technologies.
2. The government should increase funding for education and focus on technical and vocational training. With this, Nigeria can equip its citizens with the skills and knowledge needed to drive economic growth, reduce unemployment, and promote sustainable development. These investments in human capital and workforce development are critical for Nigeria's long-term economic prosperity.

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